

**THE EFFECT OF SHOPEE E-COMMERCE TRUST ON CUSTOMER LOYALTY THROUGH
THE INTERVENING VARIABLE OF PURCHASING DECISIONS (STUDY ON STUDENTS
OF THE FACULTY OF ECONOMICS AND BUSINESS, MAKASSAR STATE
UNIVERSITY)**

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of Shopee's E-Commerce Trust on Customer Loyalty in active students of the Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Negeri Makassar through Purchasing Decisions as an Intervening Variable. The sample used was 100 Shopee consumer respondents who had been selected based on predetermined criteria. The data collection technique was carried out by questionnaire and literature study. The data analysis technique consists of an Outer Model (Measurement Model) consisting of Convergent Validity, Discriminant Validity, Multicollinearity, and Composite Reliability, then the Structural Model (Inner Model) with the R-Square test, Patch Coefficients, Total Indirect Effect, and Goodness of Fit test. Based on the results of the study, it shows that the E-commerce Trust variable has a positive and significant effect on Customer Loyalty, the Purchasing Decision variable has a positive and significant effect on Customer Loyalty, the E-commerce Trust variable has a positive and significant effect on Purchasing Decisions, and the E-commerce Trust variable has a positive and significant effect on Customer Loyalty through Purchasing Decisions.

Keywords : E-commerce Trust, Purchasing Decisions, Customer Loyalty.

INTRODUCTION

E-commerce is part of a rapidly growing business model in the digital era. E-commerce offers a variety of products with varying prices and quality. In addition, e-commerce also provides convenience and comfort for consumers when shopping. Shopee is one of the online shopping services that is known to be quite comprehensive and reliable in Indonesia. Shopee's business was initially established in 2015 in Singapore and then expanded to several countries, including Indonesia (Divedigital, 2021). Shopee offers a variety of products from various categories, such as electronics, food, fashion, health, and more.

Based on data research regarding Shopee's revenue presented by Curry (2024), it displays Shopee's revenue levels for the period 2019-2023, which the researcher then presents in the form of a graph showing the annual revenue development of Shopee. Here is the display of Shopee's annual revenue graph:

Figure 1.1 Shopee's Annual Revenue Graph for the Period 2019-2023

Source: Businessofapps (2024)

In Figure 1.1, it shows the annual revenue index or gross profit of Shopee over the past 5 years with an accumulated nominal value of \$Billion or billion US dollars. Among the advantages offered by Shopee in its success are low-cost offerings for buyers and sellers, as well as a gamified application experience with discounts and vouchers as rewards. As a result, Shopee even managed to surpass Amazon and other e-commerce platforms in Southeast Asia (Curry, 2024).

In line with one of the findings of a study conducted, the factors that determine online purchasing decisions on Shopee and the factors of superiority have a significant impact on determining purchasing decisions (Widianita, 2020). Overall, in the past 5 years, Shopee has successfully increased its profits by 997.56% since 2019.

Speaking of Shopee's e-commerce, it certainly cannot be separated from the users or customers of the service itself. Along with the data acquisition above, the researcher also presents Shopee user data based on the ranking of service user quantity by country in a structured table according to the number of users.

Table Number of Shopee Users by Country 2023

Rank	Country	Users (mn)
1	Indonesia	103
2	Brazil	63
3	Vietnam	38
4	Thailand	29
5	Philippines	27
6	Taiwan	13
7	Malaysia	11
8	Mexico	8
9	Singapore	2,2

Source: Businessofapps (2024)

Based on Table 1.1, it can be seen that 9 countries have the most users on the Shopee e-commerce platform by country, with Indonesia ranking first with 103 million users. Another explanation states that the increase in online goods demand in Indonesia can be attributed to several factors, namely the rise in people's income, significant price differences, variations in consumer preferences, and the pandemic's impact, which has encouraged people to shop online (Jati et al., 2023). Another interesting fact found is that the country of origin of the company Shopee, Singapore, ranks 9th. Nevertheless, the number of users from that country is 36.34% when viewed in relation to its total population now. Indonesia itself also has 37.39% of users from its actual population, which, when viewed as a percentage, is not much different from Singapore.

Speaking of e-commerce in Indonesia, Shopee is quite popular among the general public and certainly aligns with the previous statement that also shows the large number of Shopee users in Indonesia. Here, the researcher attaches the data source regarding the

highest e-commerce visits in Indonesia:

Figure E-commerce Visit Graphs in Indonesia for the 2023 Period
Source: Databoks (2024)

Figure displays the graph of visits to e-commerce platforms in Indonesia throughout the year 2023 (Annur, 2024). In the E-commerce Visit Graph in Indonesia for the period from January to December 2023, it is evident that the Shopee platform is at the highest level. However, Shopee did experience a decline in visits in February (the 2nd month). Bima Laga, as the chairman of the Indonesia E-commerce Association (IdeA), predicted the previous year that e-commerce consumers would still hold back on spending at the beginning of the year due to economic pressures and global uncertainty, but it would grow again during Ramadan.

As for May (the 5th month), Shopee's visits temporarily decreased. The researchers indicated that the decline occurred due to a lack of interest in purchasing decisions caused by economic factors or competition from modern and traditional markets. This is supported by the decline in visit rates to other e-commerce platforms except Bukalapak. Considering that this is based on visits and not sales data, it cannot be denied that transactions could continue to increase from before even though the number of visitors has temporarily decreased.

The high level of visits to the Shopee e-commerce platform, as shown in figure 1.2, adequately reflects the level of consumer trust in observing or choosing e-commerce Shopee as the primary choice or priority of the Indonesian people in digital shopping. This term is also often referred to as e-commerce trust or e-trust. Additionally, e-commerce trust or trust in electronic commerce referring to a platform like Shopee becomes a factor that can significantly determine or influence consumers' purchasing decisions (Agustiningrum & Andjarwati 2021:902).

The e-commerce sales data in Indonesia discussed by Jayanti & Pratama (2023) indicates that the GMV in Indonesia, formed by 6 e-commerce platforms, generated a revenue of USD 51.9 billion or Rp 803.7 trillion during the year 2022. The highest sales value in e-commerce during 2022 was led by the Shopee e-commerce platform, which ranked first, surpassing Tokopedia, Lazada, Bukalapak, TikTok Shop, and Blibli. The percentage display of the Market Share value can be seen in the following image:

Figure E-Commerce Sales Data in Indonesia for the Year 2022
Source: KumparanBISNIS (2023)

Figure shows that the percentage of Shopee's e-commerce sales ranked at the top, surpassing other e-commerce platforms throughout 2022. This phenomenon may indicate a relationship between customer loyalty and purchase decisions on the Shopee online shop, as evidenced by the research conducted by Julian & Yani (2021:24), which suggests a connection between online purchase decisions and customer loyalty on the Shopee e-commerce platform.

Based on the data analysis above, the researcher is interested in discussing the factors that influence the public's interest or desire to use Shopee's services by using "e-commerce trust" as the independent variable offered as a benchmark in analyzing the dependent variable, namely "customer loyalty," using "purchase decisions" as the intervening variable.

Customer loyalty is an important factor in determining the success of a business. Customer loyalty according to Kotler (2008:138) is the attitude and behavior of consumers who tend to maintain long-term relationships with a brand, product, or service provider (Sembiring et al., 2014:4). Customer loyalty can increase profitability, market share, and business reputation.

There are several studies that discuss the impact of trust on customer loyalty, including a study conducted by Uyun (2021). The research findings reveal that trust and perceived value influence customer satisfaction, which in turn impacts loyalty. In addition, perceived trust and value also have a direct impact on customer loyalty. The research conducted by Ramadhan et al. (2024) is contrary to previous studies, where in turn Trust does not affect customer loyalty.

Another relevant study is the one conducted by Melawati et al. (2024). The study results show that e-service quality and e-trust have a positive impact on e-satisfaction. However, neither of them has a significant direct impact on e-loyalty. E-satisfaction was found to have a positive impact on e-loyalty and serves as a significant intervening

variable. Meanwhile, in the study conducted by Rintasari & Farida (2020), it was stated that there is an influence of e-trust on e-loyalty through the intervening variable e-satisfaction.

Although there are many studies discussing e-commerce trust and customer loyalty, there remains a significant research gap regarding how e-commerce trust can influence customer loyalty variables through purchase decisions, especially in the context of the Shopee platform in Indonesia. Previous studies such as Uyun (2021), Ramadhan et al. (2024), Melawati et al. (2024), and Rintasari & Farida (2020) provide insights into the relationship between trust, customer satisfaction, and loyalty. However, this research has not yet deeply explored the role of purchase decisions as an intervening factor that attempts to connect the variable of e-commerce trust with customer loyalty.

In the context of students at Makassar State University (UNM) as e-commerce consumers, there is an interesting trend related to online shopping. A study by Irmayanti et al. (2023) revealed a significant trend in online shopping among students of the Faculty of Social Sciences and Law at Makassar State University, driven by the convenience offered by e-commerce applications such as the availability of a complete range of products, low prices, and good quality. This trend is influenced by social factors (recommendations from friends and family), cultural factors (modern lifestyle), personal factors (financial conditions and hedonistic lifestyle), and psychological factors (belief in the ease of online shopping). The impact is evident in the changes in student behavior, including an increase in consumerist lifestyles and a shift towards more hedonistic living, with a tendency to use branded and trendy products that can be obtained at more affordable prices online (Irmayanti et al., 2023). These findings indicate a significant influence of e-commerce on students' shopping behavior and lifestyle, which is relevant to the researchers' focus on Shopee's e-commerce trust and its impact on customer loyalty through purchase decisions. The focus of the researchers in this case is on the students of the Faculty of Economics and Business (FEB) at Makassar State University (UNM) as the research subjects, considering the relevance and potential insights that can be obtained from this group. As students in the field of economics and business, they should generally have a superior awareness of economic concepts, consumer behavior, and digital business trends.

Furthermore, a more specific study on consumer loyalty to the Shopee e-commerce platform at FEB UNM conducted by Pratiwi et al. (2023) indicates that Shopee has a higher loyalty level compared to Tiktokshop at the Faculty of Economics and Business. So it can be concluded that there is a high level of loyalty among students of the Faculty of Economics and Business towards the online shopping application Shopee.

By focusing the research on FEB UNM students, this study will provide insights into e-commerce consumer behavior among students in general at FEB. The results of this study provide valuable contributions to the academic literature and also to e-commerce practitioners in understanding and serving the student consumer segment, particularly those with an educational background in economics and business.

Based on that background, there is still a research gap in understanding the

relationship between e-commerce trust, purchase decisions, and customer loyalty, particularly among students of the Faculty of Economics and Business at Makassar State University. This research will fill that gap by exploring how e-commerce trust influences customer loyalty through purchase decisions on the Shopee e-commerce platform.

Research on the influence of e-commerce trust on customer loyalty through purchase decisions in e-commerce is still limited, especially in Indonesia. This study was conducted to fill the existing knowledge gap by taking a case study of students from the Faculty of Economics and Business at Makassar State University. The students in this case are one of the potential consumer groups who frequently use e-commerce to meet their needs.

Based on the analysis and explanation provided earlier, the researcher has initiated a study on the Shopee online shop with the aim of understanding how e-commerce trust affects consumer loyalty towards the Shopee online shop through purchase decisions.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research uses a quantitative methodology by utilizing numerical data and statistical testing to analyze various factors that impact customer loyalty on the Shopee e-commerce platform. Quantitative research is also known as hypothesis testing research, as it is conducted by building and empirically testing hypotheses (Duryadi, 2021:11). The main focus of the research is to investigate the influence between e-commerce trust, purchase decisions, and customer loyalty.

A descriptive approach is applied in this research, where data collection is conducted using a questionnaire with a closed-ended question format and predetermined numerical answer scoring (Hamid & Anwar, 2019:140). In descriptive research, the action taken is to provide an overview of the discussion regarding the data or the scores of the measured variables (Radjab & Jam'an, 2017:125). By using this method, the research aims to generate understanding through numerical data in examining human behavior to be understood through observation and logic (Wajdi et al., 2024:16). Thus, data becomes the key element in this type of research approach to delve deeper into the dynamics of customer loyalty in the context of electronic commerce.

The population in this study is the area that the researcher intends to investigate. According to Sugiyono (2011), the population is a general area that includes objects or subjects with certain characteristics and traits that have been determined by the researcher to be studied and concluded (Patarai, 2024:50). In this study, the population used is the active students of the Faculty of Economics and Business, Makassar State University, Class of 2020-2023. The data on the number of students was obtained through the sia.unm.ac.id website. Based on the presented data sources, the total number of active students in the Faculty of Economics and Business at Makassar State University is 4,686.

A sample is a part of the population that is intended to be studied. According to Sugiyono (2011), a sample includes a portion of the quantity and characteristics possessed by the population (Patarai, 2024:50). Therefore, a sample is a part of the existing population, and sampling must use specific methods based on existing considerations

people.

The research design includes a series of systematic stages, starting from the initial preparation process to data collection, analysis, and writing the research report. Basically, the research design serves as a roadmap for researchers, providing clear and structured guidance to facilitate the efficient and effective execution of the research. With a good design, researchers can anticipate challenges, allocate resources wisely, and ensure each step aligns with the research objectives. Furthermore, a well-thought-out research design helps ensure the validity and reliability of the results, including the selection of appropriate methodologies, determination of representative samples, and comprehensive data analysis planning. A good research design demonstrates students' ability to plan and execute complex research projects with a clear and organized structure.

Data analysis is a crucial stage in research to uncover relationships between variables. This process involves processing the collected data to provide meaningful insights and serve as the basis for decision-making. The data analysis method used in this research is statistical analysis utilizing the Structural Equation Modeling-Partial Least Squares (SEM-PLS) application.

In regression techniques, the research model is built based on one dependent variable and several independent variables. When more than one dependent variable is used in the research model, other analytical tools or methods are required. These methods can solve the problem without having to create multiple regression equations, as analyzing them separately is considered less accurate. (Hamid & Ahmad, 2019:1).

The selection of SEM-PLS, particularly using SmartPLS version 4.0 software, is based on its ability to comprehensively test hypotheses. The PLS-SEM statistical technique is used to analyze the relationship between latent variables and observed variables (Hasbiah et al., 2024). SmartPLS was chosen for its advantages in explaining the relationships between latent variables, its efficiency in handling relatively small sample sizes, and its capability in analyzing complex models without assuming a specific distribution. The outer model and inner model testing methods in SEM-PLS are also excellent in analyzing unobserved latent variables and accounting for measurement errors.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Based on the testing using the SmartPLS method, the next step is to discuss the data processing results to provide a comprehensive understanding of the relationships between the research variables. The relationship includes both direct and indirect effects mediated by the intervening variable. In this case, the variables being studied are e-commerce trust (independent variable), customer loyalty (dependent variable), and purchase decision (intervening variable).

a. E-Commerce Trust (X)

Statistical calculations show a coefficient of 0.651 for the influence of e-commerce trust (X) on purchase decisions (Z), indicating a positive relationship. Through the bootstrap procedure, a coefficient estimate of 0.664 was obtained with a t-value of 11.160 and a standard deviation of 0.058. The analysis shows a p-value of 0.000 (<0.05), leading

to the acceptance of H1, which means the influence of X on Z has met the criteria for statistical significance. It can be concluded that e-commerce trust indeed has a positive impact on the purchasing decisions of students from the Faculty of Economics and Business at Makassar State University when shopping on Shopee. The significant influence of e-commerce trust on purchasing decisions aligns with consumer behavior theory, where trust is a form of perception as a psychological factor that affects the evaluation process and purchasing decisions as outlined in the Model of Consumer Behavior (Kotler & Keller 2016:187). Trust in e-commerce reduces the perception of risk and increases consumer confidence in online transactions.

As for Data analysis reveals a coefficient value of 0.464 in the test of the influence of e-commerce trust (X) on customer loyalty (Y), indicating a positive direction of the relationship. In the bootstrap procedure, a coefficient estimate of 0.475 was obtained with a t-value of 6.416 and a standard deviation of 0.072. The analysis shows a p-value of 0.000 (<0.05), making H2 accepted, which means the influence of X on Z has met the criteria for statistical significance. It can be concluded that e-commerce trust indeed has a positive impact on customer loyalty among students of the Faculty of Economics and Business at Makassar State University when shopping on Shopee, with a quite significant influence of 46.4%. These findings align with the basic concept of consumer behavior, where trust as a psychological factor plays a crucial role in forming long-term relationships. Kotler & Keller (2016:230) explain that the trust built is one of the prerequisites for enjoying a healthy long-term relationship. The positive impact of the trust built creates psychological comfort, which encourages students of the Faculty of Economics and Business at Makassar State University to remain loyal to the Shopee e-commerce platform.

Based on the questionnaire results, for the e-commerce trust variable (X), statement number 1 received the highest score with the statement "I feel that Shopee consistently provides reliable services" with a score 351 in the very high category, although there were 4 respondents who somewhat disagreed and 1 respondent who strongly disagreed. The respondents' disagreement occurred because Shopee's service was lacking in providing responses. This occurs due to variations in the consistency of Shopee's basic services experienced by users, where some users encounter differences in service quality across several of their transactions.

In statement number 2, "I believe that Shopee will promptly resolve any issues with the product I received," it received a score of 327 in the high category, despite 6 respondents being somewhat disagreeable and 1 respondent being very disagreeable. Respondents' disagreement occurred because they felt deceived or experienced delays from Shopee in responding to resolve existing issues. This occurs due to differences in effectiveness and speed in handling product issues, which involve coordination between the Shopee platform, sellers, and delivery services, thereby creating complexity in maintaining problem resolution standards.

Next, on statement number 3, "I am satisfied with the timeliness of product delivery from Shopee," with a score of 324 in the high category, although there were 15 respondents who disagreed. Respondent disagreement occurred due to delays on Shopee's part in

delivery or issues with the expedition, which slowed down the delivery process. This occurs due to variations in delivery timeliness influenced by logistical infrastructure factors in various regions, which directly impact the consistency of the delivery service received by users.

Overall, this indicates that the majority of respondents gave positive responses to those statements. However, the presence of several respondents who were somewhat and strongly disagreeing indicates that Shopee has successfully built trust among the majority of customers in terms of reliability, but there is still room for service improvement.

In the subsequent questionnaire results focusing on the honesty indicator for the e-commerce trust variable (X), statement number 4 received the lowest score with the statement "I feel that the product/service descriptions on Shopee tend to be accurate according to the received items," scoring 306 in the high category, with 20 respondents disagreeing and 1 respondent strongly disagreeing. The respondents' disagreement indicates dissatisfaction among some consumers regarding the alignment between the description and the product received. This happens because respondents feel deceived or because there is fraud on the Shopee platform, especially with items offered at prices that are usually lower than the market price.

Unlike the previous answers, in statement number 5, "I feel that Shopee is quite transparent in displaying price and promo information." Received a high score of 334 in the very high category, despite 9 respondents being less agreeable. Respondent disagreement occurs because the price or promotion displayed usually differs when they are about to purchase or checkout. This happens because shipping or expedition fees are added, which were not previously displayed in the item price, resulting in a price increase.

Next, on statement number 6, "I feel that Shopee is quite transparent in displaying promotional information" with a score of 340 in the very high category, although there were 8 respondents who disagreed. The respondents' disagreement occurred because they felt that the promotions offered were not applicable when they were about to purchase or checkout. This happens because promotions are usually given for a certain minimum threshold, so not all purchases will receive the promotion.

Differences in the assessment of the honesty indicator in the Shopee e-commerce trust variable show that overall, the majority of respondents gave positive responses to those statements. However, the presence of several respondents who disagree or strongly disagree indicates that there are still gaps in the aspect of honesty on the Shopee platform and the need for improvements in the clarity and consistency of the information provided to consumers.

In the next questionnaire results focusing on the care indicator for the e-commerce trust variable (X), statement number 7, "I feel that Shopee's customer service responds quickly and effectively in resolving issues," with a score of 312 in the high category, there were 19 respondents who disagreed. The respondents' disagreement occurred due to Shopee's delay in responding to consumer issues when there were disruptions in shopping on Shopee. The reason is due to service issues during the shopping process or because of a surge in service queues at that time, which affected the effectiveness of Shopee's

response.

In statement number 8, "I feel that Shopee is quite active in responding to user suggestions." Received a high score of 316 in the high category, despite 14 respondents being less agreeable. The respondents' disagreement occurred because of suggestions from users that they felt were ignored by Shopee. This happens because the management is either late or completely ignores consumer suggestions due to their irrelevance or being considered not beneficial in Shopee's development.

Next, on statement number 9, "I feel that Shopee is quite active in responding to user feedback," with a score of 313 in the high category, although there were 17 respondents who disagreed. The respondents' disagreement occurred due to criticism from users who felt ignored by Shopee. This happens because the management feels that not all criticism needs to be addressed, so information filtering needs to be done, especially for the development of the Shopee application.

Differences in the assessment of the attention indicator within the Shopee e-commerce trust variable indicate that, overall, the majority of respondents provided positive responses to those statements. However, the presence of some respondents who were neutral or disagreed indicates that there are negative user experiences related to Shopee's care services. This negative assessment reflects the need for improvements in the complaint handling system and user feedback management to be more responsive and effective.

In the next questionnaire results focusing on the credibility indicators for the e-commerce trust variable (X), statement number 10, which is "I feel confident that Shopee maintains the security of personal data well," received a score of 326 in the very high category, with 10 respondents disagreeing and 1 respondent strongly disagreeing. The respondents' disagreement indicates that there are specific issues in the aspect of Shopee's credibility. Regarding the security of personal data, respondents feel that their personal data could be misused, such as phone numbers and emails, for promotions that disrupt their activities.

In statement number 11, "I feel confident that Shopee maintains the security of payment information well." Received a high score of 337 in the very high category, despite 7 respondents who disagreed. The respondents' disagreement is due to uncertainty or negative experiences in the payment process. Regarding payment security, respondents have experienced transaction disruptions such as payment failures affecting their balance or delayed refunds.

Next, on statement number 12, "I feel that Shopee's reputation is already trusted among other e-commerce platforms," with a score of 348 in the very high category, although there were 6 respondents who disagreed and 1 respondent who strongly disagreed. The respondents' disagreement indicates a high level of trust in other e-commerce platforms. This happened because respondents had bad experiences such as unrealistic product sales, making them feel deceived, and the lengthy return process.

Differences in the assessment of the credibility indicator in the Shopee e-commerce trust variable show that overall, the majority of respondents provided positive responses

to those statements. However, the presence of some respondents who disagree or are neutral serves as feedback for improving credibility services.

Overall, the majority of respondents provided positive feedback on those statements. However, the presence of some respondents who disagreed or were neutral indicates that Shopee has managed to build trust among most customers, but there is still room for service improvement. These differences in assessment may be caused by varying personal experiences.

The results of this study are in line with the research conducted by Rahma & Ekowati (2022) titled "The Influence of Service Quality and Trust on Consumer Loyalty in Shopping on Shopee E-commerce," which shows that the e-trust variable has a positive and significant effect on loyalty, as evidenced by a significance value of $0.007 < 0.05$. Service quality has a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$, indicating a significant influence of service quality on consumer loyalty among Management students at Muhammadiyah University Bengkulu.

b. Customer Loyalty (Y)

The results of the statistical calculations show a coefficient of 0.451 for the influence of purchase decisions (Z) on customer loyalty (Y), indicating a positive direction of the relationship. Through the bootstrap procedure, a coefficient estimate of 0.439 was obtained with a t-value of 5.927 and a standard deviation of 0.076. The analysis shows a p-value of 0.000 (< 0.05), making H₃ accepted, which means the influence of Z on Y has met the criteria for statistical significance. It can be concluded that purchasing decisions do indeed have a positive impact on customer loyalty among students of the Faculty of Economics and Business at Makassar State University when shopping on the Shopee marketplace. Purchase decisions that positively influence loyalty reflect the learning concept in consumer behavior theory, where purchase decisions that impact post-purchase satisfaction positively encourage repeat purchase behavior (Kotler & Keller 2016:200). Thus, continuous or repeated purchases indirectly foster customer loyalty among students of the Faculty of Economics and Business at Makassar State University when shopping on Shopee.

Based on the results of the questionnaire for the repeat purchase indicator on the customer loyalty variable (Y), the statement that received the highest score is statement number 1, which is "I am used to repurchasing products on Shopee because I am satisfied with the quality" with a score of 343 in the very high category, although there were 5 respondents who disagreed. The respondents' disagreement indicates that they are not accustomed to repurchasing products on Shopee. This happens because respondents who have had unpleasant experiences related to the quality of products purchased on Shopee are not interested in buying again. Additionally, respondents might overlook the quality factor, such as price and delivery speed, leading them to respond negatively.

The results of this study are in line with the research conducted by (Nurjaya et al., 2022) titled "The Influence of Personal Selling and Price on Purchase Decisions Affecting Customer Loyalty at Lautan Surga in Jakarta, PT Lautan Surga Purchases in Jakarta," which shows that the purchase decision variable has a positive and significant effect on customer

loyalty, as evidenced by a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$. 0.05. personal selling influences purchasing decisions (39.6%), price affects purchasing decisions (37.6%), both simultaneously affecting purchase decisions (49.6%), and purchase decisions affecting customer loyalty (39.6%), all with a significance of $0.000 < 0.05$. This indicates that there is a significant influence of service quality on customer loyalty at PT. Lautan Surga Jakarta.

c. Purchase Decision (Z)

The results of the statistical calculations show an indirect effect of 0.293 for the influence of e-commerce trust (X) on customer loyalty (Y) through purchase decisions (Z), indicating a positive relationship direction. Through the bootstrap procedure, a t-value of 6.117 and a standard deviation of 0.048 were obtained. The analysis shows a p-value of 0.000 (< 0.05), leading to the acceptance of H4, which means the influence of X on Y through Z has met the criteria for statistical significance. It can be concluded that e-commerce trust indeed has a positive impact on customer loyalty through purchasing decisions by students of the Faculty of Economics and Business at Makassar State University when shopping on the Shopee marketplace. This finding reinforces the stimulus-response model in consumer behavior theory, where trust, as part of the perception in consumer psychology, acts as a stimulus that goes through the purchase decision process (Kotler & Keller 2016:187). With a positive value, the resulting response impact is in the form of loyalty, as stated that the purchase decision has an impact. post-purchase satisfaction positively encourages repeat purchase behavior (Kotler & Keller 2016:200). This process involves a complex series of consumer psychological aspects, ranging from trust formation, decision-making, to the development of loyalty.

Overall, the majority of respondents strongly agreed with the statements presented for the purchase decision variable (Z). This indicates that Shopee customers are very meticulous in their purchasing decision process. However, there is an exception in statement number 6, "I often use the seller's Q&A feature on Shopee to get more information," which received the lowest score of 317, with 12 respondents disagreeing and 4 respondents strongly disagreeing. This indicates that customers rely more on buyer reviews and price comparisons rather than direct communication with the seller in their purchasing decision process.

The results of this study are in line with the research conducted by (Welsa et al., 2024) titled "The Influence of Relationship Marketing and Customer Trust on Consumer Loyalty with Purchase Decision as an Intervening Variable: A Case Study on Aqua Mineral Water in Indonesia," which shows that the Sobel Test value of $2.49567464 > 1.96$, meaning that purchase decision can mediate the relationship between customer trust and consumer loyalty.

CONCLUSION

After observing the discussion in the previous chapter, it can be concluded as follows:

1. E-commerce trust (X) has a positive influence on purchase decisions (Z) which shows significant value. This means that e-commerce trust has a

- positive and significant effect on purchase decisions, or H1 is accepted.
2. E-commerce trust (X) has a positive effect on customer loyalty (Y) with significant value. This means that e-commerce trust has a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty, or H2 is accepted.
 3. Purchase decisions (Z) have a positive effect on customer loyalty (Y) with significant value. This means that purchase decisions have a positive and significant impact on customer loyalty, or H3 is accepted.
 4. E-commerce trust (X) has a positive effect with an assessment through an indirect effect on customer loyalty (Y) with purchase decision (Z) as the intervening variable, showing significant value. This means that e-commerce trust has a positive and significant effect on customer loyalty through purchase decisions, or H4 is accepted.

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